

**The Coaches' Eye: A Randomized Repeated-Measure Observational Study
Assessing Coaches' Perception of Velocity Loss during Resistance Training
Exercises.**

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of Master of Research at The University of the West of Scotland.**

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Abstract

Prescribing resistance training (RT) involves programming various training variables, including exercises, loads, sets, repetitions, and rest intervals (Coratella, 2022). Over the years, numerous fixed and predetermined RT programs have been developed, providing coaches with general recommendations tailored to specific populations and outcomes (Fragala et al., 2019). For example, a RT program designed to improve muscular strength in novice and intermediate trainees includes 1–3 sets of 8–12 repetitions at 70–85% of one repetition maximum (1RM) (Nuzzo et al., 2023). Importantly, fixed and predetermined RT programs typically rely on a single baseline performance measure (e.g., 1RM) taken at the start of a training cycle. While such fixed and predetermined approaches are practical at the group level (Fragala et al., 2019), they lack individualization by failing to account for between- and within-trainee day-to-day performance variability. Several factors, including fatigue (Shimano et al., 2006), sleep deprivation (Knowles et al., 2018), inadequate diet (Judelson et al., 2007), and short-term training adaptations, lead to such variability. Accordingly, fixed and predetermined RT programs do not allow for the frequent adjustments needed to account for consistent performance fluctuations, often resulting in overloading on some days and underloading on others (Judelson et al., 2007).

In RT, coaches often rely on their judgment to determine when a trainee should stop a set based on their perception in change of velocity, in line with the velocity-based training (VBT) method. However, how the coach perceives changes in velocity loss, has not been thoroughly studied. In this study, we aimed to evaluate the accuracy of RT coaches in estimating trainees' repetition velocity loss.

Twenty RT coaches participated in a single experimental session and watched a series of twenty-four video clips of two trainees (male and female), performing sets of barbell bench press and barbell back squat exercises at three different loads (45%, 65%, and 85% of 1RM) from two perspectives (front and side). They were asked to estimate when the trainees reached two velocity loss thresholds (20% and 40%) relative to the first repetition in each set. This study investigated whether velocity loss threshold, load, view, mental fatigue, and gaze strategy influenced estimation accuracy. We compared outcomes using a negative binomial generalized mixed effects model.

Across all conditions, the average absolute accuracy error was 2.6 repetitions, with individual errors ranging from 1 to 5 repetitions. Coaches showed improved accuracy when estimating a higher velocity loss threshold (40% vs 20%; -1.8 , 95%CI [-2.3 , -1.3]), using heavier loads (-0.8 , 95%CI [-1.5 , -0.1]) for 65% 1RM, and -3 , 95%CI [-3.4 , -2.6] for 85% 1RM compared to 45% 1RM), and when employing a bar tracking gaze strategy compared to a no-bar strategy (-1.7 , 95%CI [-2.7 , -0.4]). These findings were consistent across both perspectives, with mental fatigue having a minimal impact.

While coaches can perceive velocity loss with a certain degree of accuracy, their error rates vary depending on the velocity loss threshold, load, and gaze strategy used. Coaches should take these error rates into consideration when applying perceived velocity loss in their training practices.

Background

Resistance training (RT), also referred to as strength or weight training, has gained widespread recognition among sports scientists and strength and conditioning coaches (SCCs) as an effective method for improving athletic performance. Dumont (2005) emphasised the importance of RT to induce significant physiological adaptations beneficial to both competitive athletes and the general population. The process of designing and implementing RT programs is intricate, requiring coaches to carefully manipulate various variables, including exercise selection, load (intensity), volume (sets and repetitions), and rest intervals, tailored to the individual needs of each athlete.

Traditionally, pre-designed RT programs have been investigated in research (Carpinelli, 2009), providing coaches and practitioners with comprehensive guidelines tailored to the needs of distinct populations and training outcomes (Fisher et al., 2011). These programs consider a range of variables such as age, gender, fitness level, and specific athletic goals, ensuring not only effective training but also adaptability to the unique physiological and psychological needs of various groups, including elite athletes, general fitness enthusiasts, and individuals undergoing rehabilitation (Kibele & Behm, 2009; Tomljanović et al., 2011).

However, recent studies have highlighted limitations of traditional RT approaches, such as lack of individualisation and failure to account for the daily fluctuations in the individual's performance. This, in turn, can lead to training plateaus and limited progress (Garber et al., 2011; Ghobadi et al., 2021; Lew & Qu, 2014). This stagnation is often attributed to a lack of variation in the training stimulus, and the "one-size-fits-all" model fails to adequately address the unique needs, goals, and responses of individual athletes (Hoffman et al., 2009). Consequently, amended RT programming must continue to pursue individualized approaches and progressive variation to drive further adaptations for athletic development and general fitness.

Researchers suggest that RT can be further personalized through auto-regulation approaches, which involves adjusting training variables (sets, reps, intensity/load, and rest intervals) based on real-time responses collected during the RT session (Larsen, Kristiansen, & van den Tillaar, 2021; Greig et al., 2020). Autoregulation is based on the foundational principle that an individual's readiness, as well as daily variations in physical and mental states, significantly

impact performance outcomes (Nevin, 2019). By modifying workout parameters—such as load, repetitions, and rest intervals—in real-time, autoregulation accommodates variables such as fatigue, recovery, stress, and physiological adaptation. This method enhances training efficiency by ensuring that athletes avoid both overtraining and undertraining, ultimately promoting more effective performance gains (Greig et al., 2020). Practically, autoregulation can be implemented through subjective and objective methods (Larsen et al., 2021). Subjective approaches, such as the Rating of Perceived Exertion (RPE), Repetition in Reserve (RIR) rely on the athlete's self-assessment of their exertion during a training session. In contrast, objective techniques, such as barbell velocity tracking, utilize quantifiable data to adjust the load and intensity based on performance metrics. These methods provide data-driven feedback that informs training modifications (Shattock & Tee, 2022). Autoregulation, also allows practitioners to account for the daily fluctuations in an athlete's performance capacity, incorporating factors such as training-induced fatigue, external stressors, and recovery processes. This approach enables athletes to adjust to real-time feedback, ensuring they train within their optimal zone for adaptation and performance enhancement (Larsen et al., 2021).

VBT relies upon measuring the velocity outputs of repetitions during various exercises and manipulating resistance training programming and constituent variables accordingly (Dorrell, Smith, & Gee, 2020; Orange et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022). Velocity loss threshold (VLT) refers to the predetermined percentage decline in concentric repetition velocity relative to the first (fastest) repetition in a set. It is a central variable in velocity-based training (VBT) used to regulate training volume and intensity. For example, a 20% VLT indicates that the set is terminated when the repetition velocity drops by 20%, allowing practitioners to control the degree of neuromuscular fatigue while targeting specific training outcomes such as strength, power, or hypertrophy (Jukic et al., 2022; Pareja-Blanco et al., 2020). Various velocity thresholds are utilized in resistance training to achieve specific training goal outcomes. Research indicates that a 20% velocity loss threshold, is optimal for maximizing strength and power outputs, while minimizing fatigue, allowing for quick recovery and making it suitable for strength and power training (Jukic et al., 2022). Meanwhile, research has stated a higher velocity loss threshold of 40%, is commonly used during hypertrophy-focused training phases. By utilizing this approach, athletes generate greater muscle mass. However, a 40% velocity

threshold leads to increased fatigue and metabolic stress on the athlete (Pareja-Blanco et al., 2020).

However, to implement VBT effectively, valid and reliable velocity-tracking technologies, such as accelerometers, linear position and velocity transducers, and smartphone applications, are required (Weakley et al., 2020). While these technologies are widely available, portable, and mostly affordable, their use can be impractical in large groups where multiple trainees share the same equipment (e.g., machines or lifting platforms) or when trainees must transition quickly between exercises.

Recently, the trainee's perception of velocity loss has been explored as an alternative to the direct measurement of repetition velocity. This involves trainees subjectively estimating the repetition at which velocity decreases below a fixed threshold (e.g., 20%) relative to an anchor repetition. For example, Shaw et al 2023, asked trainees to verbally report the repetition associated with a 20% velocity loss relative to the first repetition in a set while performing deadlifts at 60% and 80% of 1RM (Shaw et al. 2023). Similarly, Dello Iacono et al (2023), investigated perceptions of velocity loss at 20% and 40% thresholds across the entire load-velocity spectrum during the barbell bench press (Dello Iacono et al. 2023). Both studies compared perceived velocity loss against actual velocity measurements. The results showed that trainees' absolute errors were mostly within 1.5 repetitions on average, with medium to large individual variations.

While these studies advance the integration of subjective perception of velocity into RT practice, they have only focused on trainees' perception of velocity loss. In practice, RT coaches also instruct trainees to terminate sets based on observable signs such as technique breakdown, visible fatigue, and perceived decreases in repetition velocity—decisions that are inherently aligned with velocity-based training (VBT) principles. Although objective VBT tools (e.g., linear position transducers) provide precise feedback, their cost, technical demands, and impracticality in large-group settings often limit their accessibility in applied environments (Guppy et al., 2023; Moreno-Villanueva et al., 2021). In contrast, the coach's perception of velocity loss (PVL) offers a tech-free alternative enabling to implement autoregulation without relying on self-assessment or expensive technology. If proven accurate, the coach's PVL could serve as a practical, low-cost autoregulation means—

particularly valuable when objective tools are unavailable or when working with novice trainees who struggle with their perception of velocity or effort.

Therefore, the aim of this study was to assess coaches' accuracy in perceiving repetition velocity loss— hereby referred to as the “coach's eye”. To this aim, we recruited RT coaches and presented them with videos of two trainees performing three sets of two exercises at three incremental loads, recorded from two different views. Coaches were asked to report the repetitions they perceived as corresponding to 20% and 40% velocity loss. We examined whether velocity loss threshold, load, view, mental fatigue, and coaches' gaze strategy influenced the accuracy of the coach's eye. Given the lack of evidence on this topic, we employed an observational study design and did not formulate any a-priori hypotheses regarding the effects of the variables of interest on the primary outcome. However, we selected the following variables based on their practical relevance and theoretical rationale: Velocity loss thresholds of 20% and 40%, as these are the most used in VBT to enhance neuromuscular adaptations. Loads corresponding to 45%, 65%, and 85% of 1RM, to represent a broad range of intensities typically prescribed in RT.

Methods

Research Design

The philosophical grounding for this research is the pragmatism paradigm. This approach was chosen as it is orientated to applied practice as it primarily focuses on the research problem and the consequences of the research. It allows for real world practice to inform research and research to inform real world practice, thus closing the gap between academic work and applied practice (Giacobbi, Poczwardowski & Hager, 2005).

This study employed a randomized, repeated-measures observational design to examine coaches' accuracy in perceiving velocity loss under different resistance training conditions such as exercises, loads, VLTs and points of observation.

Sample size and participants

The sample size calculation was based on the precision-for-planning approach described by Cumming (Cumming, 2012). This method requires specifying the target margin of error and the confidence interval of the estimate of interest to compute an accurate sample size. Two key parameters are needed for this calculation: (1) the expected standard deviation (σ) and (2) the magnitude of the parameter estimate (e.g., coach's eye accuracy) considered meaningful in the study's context. Due to the lack of existing data on coaches' accuracy in perceiving repetition velocity loss, we utilized a σ equal to 0.75 repetitions as reported by Dello Iacono et al. (2023), who studied perception accuracy among trainees rather than coaches. Based on our judgment and domain expertise in resistance training and considering the typical repetition range (4-12) prescribed in such programs, we deemed an accuracy error of 1 repetition as practically meaningful (e.g., corresponding to 8-25% of set volume). The sample size was then estimated using the following formula:

$$N = \left(\frac{t_{critical} \times (N-1)}{f} \right)^2 \times (\chi^2_{critical} \times (N-1))$$

Where:

- $t_{critical}$ is the critical value of the t-distribution at a 95% confidence interval, required because the population (i.e., coaches) standard deviation is unknown.

- f is the ratio between the practically meaningful magnitude (1 repetition) and the standard deviation ($\sigma = 0.75$). In this study, f was ~ 1.3333 .
- χ^2_{critical} is the critical value of the chi-square distribution, used to adjust the sample size calculation and increase the assurance (with 99% probability) that the observed margin of error in the new study will not exceed the pre-defined margin.

Based on this calculation, a sample size of 20 qualified RT coaches were recruited, who volunteered to participate in the study (Table 1). Written informed consent was obtained after the participants received an oral explanation of the purpose and potential risks of the study. All procedures were approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of the West of Scotland (approval number: 2024-16384).

Table 1: Coaches' demographics (mean \pm SD)

Age (years)	28.6 \pm 6.8
Gender	18M and 2F
Hours of RT coaching per week	7.9 \pm 6.6
Experience with VBT (Yes/No)	11/9

SD: standard deviation; RT: resistance training; VBT: velocity-based training

Procedures

Participants attended the laboratory for a single experimental session. First, we briefed them on the study procedure and obtained informed consent. Next, we assisted the participants in putting on the eye-tracking glasses, calibrated the devices, and familiarized the participants with the study procedures by having them practice with 2 videos featuring a different trainee than those in the experiment. During the habituation they also practiced using the mental fatigue scale. Once familiarization was complete, participants watched 24 videos featuring 2 trainees (one male and one female), performing 2 RT exercises (Barbell bench press and barbell back squat), over 3 loads (45%, 65%, and 85% 1RM) and from 2 viewpoints (Front and Side). Each video clip, lasting between 27 seconds to 79 seconds in

total. The rationale for the use of the loads corresponding to 45%, 65%, and 85% of 1RM, is that they represent a broad range of intensities typically prescribed in RT to induce neuromuscular and morphological adaptations (e.g., rate of force development, maximal strength, and hypertrophy (Kraemer and Ratamess, 2004; Cormie et al., 2011; Suchomel et al., 2016).

The upward (concentric) phase of each repetition was performed as fast as possible, and the set was terminated at self-assessed task failure—defined as when the trainee could no longer or was unwilling to complete another repetition. The order of the videos was randomized with respect to trainees, exercises, and points of view, while the loads were always presented in a fixed sequence: 45% 1RM first, 65% 1RM second, and 85% 1RM last. The videos were projected onto a large screen (4 × 1.5 meters) in a quiet environment with the audio muted. Participants stood 3 meters from the screen and were instructed to indicate (by saying “stop”) the repetition at which they perceived a 20% or 40% decrease in bar velocity compared to the first repetition (Figure 1). Not all videos included both 20% and 40% velocity decreases; some included only a 20% decrease, while others included neither. This information was provided to participants before the session began. Immediately after each answer, or at the end of the video if no answer was given, the researcher paused the video, noted the repetition number, and asked participants to rate their perceived mental fatigue using a visual analog scale. Participants then had a standardized 30-second break before resuming the experiment. The duration of the experiment varied between 43 and 52 minutes across participants. At the end of the session, participants provided information about their experience with the VBT method and their weekly coaching hours.

Figure 1: Experimental setup.

Participants stood approximately 3 meters from the large screen, wearing eye-tracking glasses to track their gaze. The researcher, seated quietly in the corner of the room, controlled the display on the screen, ensuring minimal distraction while managing the experimental setup.

Trainees

The two trainees featured in the videos had at least 5 years of RT experience and routinely trained at least three times per week. They reported to a laboratory for a single session, which included a 1RM assessment for the barbell back squat and barbell bench press exercises, followed by three sets of each exercise loaded at 45%, 65%, and 85% of 1RM and performed to task failure (see definition above). Trainees were instructed to avoid intense RT sessions involving the same exercises within 24 hours before testing to prevent muscle soreness or

performance decrements. Additionally, they were asked to refrain from heavy meals, caffeine, or ergogenic supplements for at least 2 hours before the session.

At the beginning of the session, the trainees completed an 8-minute general warm-up consisting of 5 minutes of individualized, self-selected warm-up on either a cycle ergometer or arm ergometer, followed by 3 minutes of dynamic stretching for upper and lower body muscles. This was followed by an exercise-specific warm-up, which involved 2–4 sets of 2–3 repetitions each, with progressively heavier loads (velocity range: 1.4–0.3 m·s⁻¹). To estimate 1RM, the velocity-based protocol proposed by Loturco et al. (2021) was employed, owing to its demonstrated practicality, safety, and ecological validity in athletic contexts. This method facilitates the accurate prediction of maximal strength using submaximal loads and corresponding barbell velocity measurements.

After a 10-minute rest, the trainees performed three sets of each exercise to task failure, starting with the heaviest load and progressing to the lightest (i.e., 85%-65%-45% 1RM) to avoid induce uniform fatigue effects between sets across all the participants. These were instructed to perform the concentric phase of each repetition as fast as possible, while maintaining a controlled descent of approximately 2 seconds until touching a bench (barbell back squat; adjusted to ensure a knee angle of 80-90 degrees) or their chest (barbell bench press). An 8-minute rest period was provided between sets and exercises. Barbell velocity during the concentric phase of each repetition was recorded using a linear encoder attached with a string tether to the end of the barbell and perpendicular to the ground.

Video recordings

Video recordings were captured using two high-quality digital video cameras (Casio Exilim 100, Casio, Japan) mounted on tripods and positioned in the frontal (front view) and sagittal (side view at a 90-degree angle) planes, at distances of 3 meters and 2 meters, respectively. These angles and distances were chosen to: 1) replicate the typical observational positions used by RT coaches in practice, and 2) provide relevant information for analysing the participants' gaze strategies during the experimental task.

Mental fatigue

Participants were asked to report their mental fatigue (“How much mentally fatigue are you?”) using a 0 (“no fatigue”) to 100 (“maximal fatigue – I can’t carry on the task”) visual analog scale (Lee et al., 1991). An electronic version of the scale was projected on the screen immediately after each answer, and/or at the end of the video in the case the participants provided no answer regarding the perception of velocity loss.

Eye tracking

The Tobii Pro Glasses 3 (Tobii Technology, Danderyd, Sweden), lightweight head-mounted glasses (77 grams), were used to track coaches' gaze at a sampling rate of 100 Hz. The glasses feature a forward-facing scene camera that records the participant's field of view at 25 frames per second with a resolution of 1920×1080 pixels. The glasses were fitted to each participant and calibrated using the Tobii Pro Glasses Controller software (firmware version 1.19.1). Calibration was conducted by instructing participants to focus their gaze on a black dot located on a calibration card, positioned 1 meter away.

Participant gaze tracking was employed to enhance understanding of the perceptual and attentional mechanisms underpinning coaches’ estimations of repetition velocity loss. This methodological choice aligns with emerging literature that highlights the role of gaze in motor control and decision-making accuracy in applied sport settings (Vickers, 2007; Hüttermann et al., 2018). Given the visually dynamic and time-sensitive nature of RT, assessing gaze strategy allowed for the exploration of how coaches interpret kinematic cues and regulate attentional resources under varying load and fatigue conditions. The inclusion of gaze tracking further supports the study's ecological validity by capturing behaviours that mirror real-time observational demands encountered in practice.

Post-experiment analysis was performed using Tobii Pro Lab Analyzer software (version 1.24.54542). A built-in fixation filter was applied to the gaze data, which displayed a red circle on the gaze video to indicate fixations. Manual coding was conducted using the gaze video to analyse the concentric phase of each lift. The fixation duration was recorded relative to predefined areas of interest, including the bar, weight plates, lifter’s body, and any other environmental features, such as wall markings. For analysis, these areas were collapsed into

two categories: "bar" (the bar, weight plates and ring) and "no bar" (lifter body, environmental feature, any other area). When the participant's fixation was directed at the bar or attached weight plates for > 50% of the overall fixation duration for the concentric phase of the lift, the strategy was classified as a "bar strategy". Otherwise, the strategy classified as "no-bar" strategy.

Statistical analysis

The outcome measure in this study—coaches' eye accuracy—was defined as the absolute error between the perceived repetitions (as reported by the coach) and the actual repetitions (measured via the linear encoder) at which velocity exceeded the 20% and 40% loss thresholds. For example, if a 20% velocity loss occurred at the 6th repetition and a coach reported it at the 8th repetition, the absolute error would be 2 repetitions. When a coach did not provide a response regarding perceived velocity loss, accuracy was calculated as the absolute difference from the total number of repetitions completed by the trainee. For instance, if a 40% velocity loss occurred at the 12th out of 15 repetitions, and the coach did not indicate any repetition, the absolute error would be 3 repetitions. The same method was applied when neither 20% nor 40% velocity losses were reported. If a coach indicated repetitions exceeding the velocity loss thresholds when such a loss did not occur, the error was calculated similarly. For example, if a coach reported a 40% velocity loss occurring at the 8th repetition when it did not occur at all out of a total of 12 repetitions, the absolute error would be 4 repetitions.

Accuracy was treated as discrete count data, with a lower bound of zero (perfect accuracy) and no theoretical upper bound (indicating lower accuracy). Exploratory data analysis revealed that the data was right-skewed and over dispersed, with variance considerably larger than the mean of the outcome measure. Consequently, we fitted a negative binomial generalized linear mixed-effects regression model, specifying a negative binomial error distribution with a log-link function (Roback & Legler, 2021), to examine the odds associated with the predictors: load, view, velocity loss threshold, coaches' tracking strategy, mental fatigue, and order of videos. The following regression model was fitted:

$$accuracy_{in} = b_{0in} + b_{1-3}load + b_{4-5}view + b_{6-7}velocity\ loss\ threshold + b_{8-9}strategy + b_{10}mental\ fatigue + b_{11}order + \varepsilon_{in}$$

Here, *accuracy* represented the repeated-measures outcome for each coach, while *load* (a categorical variable with 3 levels: 45% 1RM, 65% 1RM, 85% 1RM), *view* (a categorical variable with 2 levels: front, side), *velocity loss threshold* (a categorical variable with 2 levels: 20%, 40%), and *strategy* (a categorical variable with 2 levels: no-bar, bar) were modelled as fixed effects. *Mental fatigue* and the *order* of videos were included as continuous predictors to account for their effects on the outcome measure. The final regression model also included random intercepts for each coach and random slopes for mental fatigue and strategy to account for the dependencies of each coach, as they provided repeated accuracy ratings. Akaike information criterion score was examined to confirm the selection of the final model to obtain the best-fit model while maintaining model parsimony (See R statistical analysis code script available online at: <https://osf.io/sjzrn>). Estimated marginal means and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated alongside comparisons made using post-hoc Tukey adjustments. Significance was set at $p < 0.05$. To validate the assumptions of the negative binomial generalized linear mixed-effects model, tests for uniformity of residuals, outliers and zero-inflation were performed using a simulation-based approach, which confirmed the absence of significant violations of the model fit (Hartig, 2016). All statistical analyses were conducted in R language and environment for statistical computing using the *glmer*, *DHARMA*, *emmeans*, and *ggeffects* packages, while model assumptions were checked using the *performance* package (4.0.5; R Core Team, Vienna, Austria). The datasets used in this study are available online at: <https://osf.io/m9gds>.

Results

Descriptive data from the experimental session are presented as means (SD) and range intervals in table 2 while the accuracy scores for each coach are illustrated in figure 2. The average absolute accuracy error was 2.6 repetitions (SD = 3.4; range: 0–20) across all loads, views, velocity loss thresholds, and strategies. To aid interpretation of the results, we present the exponentiated odds and odds ratios of the model outputs as marginal average accuracy errors and pairwise comparisons between levels of the fixed effects, expressed in number of repetitions (Table 3). The model's intercept was estimated at 5.3 (95%CI [3.6, 7.6]), representing the average absolute accuracy error in perceiving a 20% velocity loss during sets loaded at 45% 1RM, observed from the front view, using a no-bar tracking strategy. Perceiving repetitions corresponding to a 40% velocity loss, as opposed to 20%, reduced the error by -1.8 (95%CI [-2.3, -1.3]). Videos filmed from the side view had a minimal impact on accuracy compared to the front view (-0.4; 95%CI [-1.2, 0.5]). Increasing the load to 65% 1RM and 85% 1RM further decreased the error by -0.8 (95%CI [-1.5, -0.1]) and -3 (95%CI [-3.4, -2.6]), respectively. Using a bar tracking strategy also reduced the error by -1.7 (95%CI [-2.7, -0.4]). Lastly, the model showed trivial effects for both mental fatigue (-0.1; 95%CI [-0.1, 0]) and order of video presentation (0.1; 95%CI [-0.1, 0.1]).

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of coaches' accuracy error across velocity loss thresholds, loads, views and strategies

	Mean (SD); Range
Velocity loss	
20%	2.96 (3.18); 0-15
40%	2.26 (3.57); 0-20
Load	
45% 1RM	3.69 (4.7); 0-20
65% 1RM	2.79 (2.72); 0-15
85% 1RM	1.35 (1.53); 0-9
View	
Front	2.58 (3.39); 0-20
Side	2.64 (3.4); 0-19
Strategy	
No-bar	3.06 (3.5); 0-20
Bar	2.15 (3.22); 0-17

SD: standard deviation

Table 3: Negative binomial generalized mixed-effects linear regression model outputs on coaches' accuracy

Variable	Estimate	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper	P value
Intercept	5.3	3.6	7.6	<0.001*
Velocity Loss (40% vs 20%)	-1.8	-2.3	-1.3	<0.001*
View (Side vs front)	-0.4	-1.2	0.5	0.389
Load (65% 1RM vs 45% 1RM)	-0.8	-1.5	-0.1	0.034*
Load (85% 1RM vs 45% 1RM)	-3	-3.4	-2.6	<0.001*
Strategy (Bar vs no-bar)	-1.7	-2.7	-0.4	0.012*
Cognitive fatigue	-0.1	-0.1	0	0.097
Order	0	-0.1	0.1	0.964
Random effects				
$\sigma^2 = 2.2$				
$\tau_{\text{coach}} = 1.5$				
$\tau_{\text{fatigue}} = 0$				
$\tau_{\text{bar strategy}} = 1.4$				
$\rho = -0.41$				
N = 20				
Observations = 960				
Marginal $R^2 = 0.204$				
Conditional $R^2 = 0.375$				

*P-value < 0.05

CI: confidence interval

Intercept: 20% VL at 45% 1RM observed from front view using a no-bar tracking strategy

σ^2 : within-subject variability

τ_{coach} : between-coach intercept variability

τ_{fatigue} : between-coach fatigue variability

$\tau_{\text{bar strategy}}$: between-coach bar variability

ρ : intercept-slope correlation

Discussion

We assessed coaches' accuracy in perceiving repetition velocity loss as they observed trainees performing three sets of two exercises at three different loads. The average accuracy error was 2.6 repetitions across all velocity loss thresholds, loads, views, and bar tracking strategies. Accuracy improved when coaches perceived a higher velocity loss threshold, observed exercises with heavier loads, and adopted a bar tracking strategy. These findings were consistent across both points of view, with mental fatigue and the order of repeated tasks having negligible impact.

Coaches' accuracy improved when perceiving repetitions corresponding to a 40% velocity loss compared to 20% velocity loss. The main reason resides in the repetition-velocity loss profile, which typically develops in a progressive manner during RT exercises. As a set progresses, velocity decrements are greater between consecutive repetitions around higher velocity loss thresholds (e.g., $\geq 40\%$) compared to lower ones (e.g., $\leq 20\%$) (Jukic et al., 2023). Coaches were likely able to perceive this more pronounced decrease in movement velocity, leading to improved accuracy. This reason may also explain the improvement in accuracy under heavier loads, where the velocity loss per additional repetition is even more substantial due to the lower number of repetitions that can be performed in a set (Nuzzo et al., 2023). For instance, when lifting at 85% of one-repetition maximum, an athlete may only be able to perform 4–6 repetitions before failure, resulting in a sharper decline in velocity with each rep compared to lifting at 60%, where 12–15 repetitions are possible and the velocity loss per rep is more gradual. When observing trainees performing exercises loaded with 45% 1RM, coaches may misjudge a 20% and 40% velocity loss by approximately 5 and 3 repetitions, respectively. These errors are reduced with heavier loads, where errors of 4 and 2 repetitions are expected for 65% 1RM, and 2 and less than 1 repetition for 85% 1RM, respectively. This suggests that a case-by-case judgment would be required when considering the use of perceived velocity loss as an alternative to velocity tracking technology for implementing the VBT method in RT practice. For instance, while an error of 1 repetition is likely negligible in sets loaded with 85% 1RM and targeting a 40% velocity loss—where a total of 8 repetitions is expected—an error of 4 repetitions could be meaningful in sets loaded with 65% 1RM and targeting a 20% velocity loss, where only 6 repetitions are expected. Therefore, coaches must determine whether their error rates are acceptable based on their overall RT goals.

The results show that by using a bar tracking strategy significantly improved accuracy rates, reducing the absolute error by approximately 2 repetitions. Notably, coaches were not given any instructions about which strategy to use before the study, nor did they receive feedback during the experimental tasks. This implies we may not have enough data to suggest a bar strategy approach, is superior. Most coaches alternated between no-bar and bar tracking strategies randomly, without a systematic pattern across exercises, velocity loss thresholds, loads, or views (Figure 2). These findings highlight that there is potential to explore whether the bar strategy is trainable and if it is trainable to test whether it can be effectively adopted consistently between participants. To the best of the author's knowledge, this is the first study to assess coaches' accuracy in detecting trainees' velocity loss. Although no previous studies have directly investigated this, the findings can be compared to research examining similar tasks, such as how accurately trainees perceive their own velocity loss. For instance, Dello Iacono and colleagues assessed trainees' accuracy in detecting 20% and 40% velocity loss during the bench press, reporting an average absolute error of 1 repetition (Dello Iacono et al., 2023). Similarly, Shaw and colleagues examined 20% velocity loss detection during deadlifts at 60% and 80% 1RM, with an average error of 1.4 repetitions (Shaw et al., 2023). In contrast, we observed a larger average error of 2.6 repetitions, suggesting trainees may be more accurate than coaches. However, our findings showed coaches' accuracy improved with heavier loads, whereas Dello Iacono and colleagues reported a decline under the same conditions (Dello Iacono et al., 2023), and Shaw and colleagues observed no difference (Shaw et al., 2023). We also found higher accuracy at the 40% threshold, whereas Dello Iacono and colleagues found no effect of threshold. This strengthens the recommendation for a case-by-case judgment when considering the use of perceived velocity loss as an alternative to velocity-tracking technology.

The analysis of random effects (Table 3), examining the within-coach relationship between the intercept (i.e., bar strategy estimate) and the slope (i.e., bar vs. no-bar tracking strategy difference), supports this assumption (Brown, 2021). The negative correlation coefficient ($\rho = -0.41$) between intercept and slope suggests that coaches who were less accurate with the no-bar tracking strategy (i.e., higher intercept) showed greater improvement when switching to a bar tracking strategy (i.e., larger negative slope). This pattern is consistent

with findings from training and skill acquisition literature, where individuals with lower baseline performance often demonstrate greater learning gains (Ericsson, 2008; McNamara & Bransford, 2000). It also reflects a well-documented compensatory effect observed in perceptual-motor tasks (Wulf & Shea, 2002), where guided strategies help to scaffold performance more effectively for lower-skilled individuals. Collectively, these findings are encouraging, as they indicate that with clear instructions and training, a bar-only approach strategy may be especially beneficial for improving accuracy among less accurate coaches. However, we observed that coaches' accuracy improved with heavier loads and at the 40% VL threshold. These findings likely reflect multiple interacting mechanisms. Physiologically, heavier loads tend to induce more overt neuromuscular fatigue (Enoka & Duchateau, 2008). From a biomechanical standpoint, reductions in bar velocity and alterations in concentric tempo are more pronounced at higher intensities, offering clearer external cues for coaches to detect specific VLT.

Together, these findings emphasize the complex interplay of physiological fatigue markers, biomechanical expression of effort, and cognitive-perceptual processing in determining coaching accuracy. They also support the recommendation for context-specific judgments when using perceived velocity loss as a proxy for objective monitoring.

This study has several limitations worthy of discussion. First, coaches usually watch trainees perform exercises live rather than on a screen. Future research should explore how well coaches can perceive repetition velocity loss in RT settings rather than relying on video recordings. Second, the calculation method for absolute error when the velocity threshold was not exceeded may underestimate the true error. If a coach incorrectly judged the threshold to be reached near the end of a set, the resulting error might appear small due to the few remaining repetitions, even though the trainee could have performed more. This calculation approach does not account for how many additional repetitions could have been completed before exceeding the velocity threshold. However, since trainees terminated the set voluntarily the true extent of the error remains unknown. Third, we were unable to examine the effects of VBT experience on accuracy rates due to the small sample size. However, it is important to note that coaches with experience in VBT may not necessarily have an advantage over those without such experience. Typical VBT practice relies heavily on tracking devices that provide immediate augmented feedback. This can limit opportunities

for coaches to refine their observational skills, potentially diminishing the benefits of VBT experience in accurately perceiving velocity loss during RT. The findings of Emanuel et al regarding the trivial effect of experience on accuracy, further support this notion (Emanuel et al., 2022). Finally, the videos included only two exercises, with coaches asked to perceive velocity loss at 20% and 40%. Therefore, it remains unclear whether our findings can be generalized to other exercises and velocity loss thresholds.

Conclusion

The study presents a pioneering contribution to existing literature by being the first to scrutinize the accuracy of coaches in discerning repetition velocity loss during resistance training. Results indicate that the average errors in accuracy varied from one to five repetitions across the diverse conditions evaluated. Significantly, accuracy exhibited enhancement under specific circumstances: when coaches were charged with appraising higher velocity loss thresholds, when exercises were executed with heavier loads, and when a bar-tracking strategy was utilized. These findings hold substantial practical implications, indicating that coaches are proficient in leveraging their perception of velocity loss to implement velocity-based training (VBT) methodologies. Nevertheless, to maximize effectiveness, coaches must remain cognizant of the inherent error rates and modify their approaches correspondingly to align with their broader resistance training objectives. As a result, this research underscores the importance of refining observational strategies and error management when applying VBT principles in practice.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1K7IINT5eWNzLJE7DG-GI2gsiiYv8Sr22?usp=sharing>

Appendix 2

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1neIKE4wV2vTX81fWJ-ruim6zMcJ4tz7h?usp=sharing>

Appendix 3

https://drive.google.com/file/d/13xVL7N94_84q8h-0qatcn8_k6TLJAlgD/view?usp=sharing

Appendix 4

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1ZJGYAW63vRSEtyloH3_QgTBDrl0GJegh?usp=sharing

Appendix 5

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/120hsLLVNmqxHKF767ZDz29qFTT1cTQOI?usp=sharing>

Appendix 6

Figure 2: Individual coach accuracy error scores grouped by gaze strategy.

